

ANTIBIOGRAM AND EVALUATION OF ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITY OF *COCHLOSPERMUM PLANCHONII* (ROOT), ON PULMONARY BACTERIAL CO-INFECTION IN COVID-19 PATIENTS IN JOS, PLATEAU STATE, NIGERIA.

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Abstract

Bacterial infection is an important co-morbidity in pulmonary viral infection and the novel Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) presents a seemingly new challenge in global healthcare. This study aimed to determine the antibacterial activity of *Cochlospermum planchonii* root on pulmonary bacterial co-infection in COVID-19 patients. Methanolic extracts of *Cochlospermum planchonii* root was used for the analysis. Kirby-Bauer disc diffusion method, Agar Well Diffusion (AWD), Minimum Inhibitory Concentration (MIC), and Minimum Bactericidal Concentration (MBC) techniques according to established standards were used to analyze the susceptibility properties of the plant extract on the clinical isolates. Antioxidant studies of the fractionated 100% Methanol extract component were carried out using 2,2-di-phenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH), Total Oxyradical Scavenging Capacity and the Total Phenolic Content of the extracts were estimated. Sputum samples from a total number of 1,620 patients were collected and analyzed with standard microbiological techniques to isolate and identify the bacterial species. Of the bacterial pathogens isolated, 13.98% were *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, 38.71% were *Staphylococcus aureus*, 22.58% were *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 16.13%, while *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* was 1.06% and Non-Tuberculous *Mycobacteria* was 7.53%. Susceptibility testing of the clinical isolates was done with conventional antibiotic discs and with the plant extract. The methanol extract showed an impressive Mean Diameter Zone of inhibition and a statistically significant difference at $P < 0.05$. The MBC/MIC ratio was 2, showing that the plant is both inhibitory and bactericidal. This study proves pulmonary bacterial coinfection in COVID-19, provides a reference antibiogram, and establishes the efficacy of *Cochlospermum planchonii*, in combating pulmonary bacterial infections in COVID-19 patient.

Keywords: Antibiogram; Antibacterial activities; *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root; COVID-19, Disc Diffusion, Agar Well Diffusion, Diameter Zone of Inhibition, Antioxidant studies.

Introduction

Bacteria co-infection is an important co-morbidity in pulmonary viral infection. SARS-CoV-2 or COVID-19 (respiratory pneumonia), started on December 15, 2019 in Wuhan City, Hubei Province, south of the People's Republic of China (Chan et al., 2020). Pulmonary diseases of viral origin are often followed by the manifestation of secondary infections, leading to further clinical complications and negative disease outcomes (Manohar et al., 2020). Viruses causing respiratory tract infections have been the cause of high morbidities and mortality rates worldwide, often in a seasonal manner for decades (Bradley and Bryan, 2019). One major complication of viral infections, especially pulmonary viruses, is colonization of the viral affected organs by bacteria which is associated with high morbidity and mortality rates, following a weakened immune response and/or opportunistic and accessible routes of entry for bacterial pathogen(s) (Mallia et al., 2012). While secondary bacterial infections or superinfections are largely a consequence of immune susceptibility caused by the primary viral infection, co-infections are multiple infections (viral/bacterial/yeast) that occur simultaneously. Common bacteria isolated during secondary infections include *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Streptococcus pneumoniae*, *Neisseria meningitidis*, *Hemophilus influenzae*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae* and members of the *Proteus*, *Acinetobacter* spp., *Pseudomonas* spp., *Enterobacter* and *Citrobacter* spp (Manohar et al., 2020). During active viral infections, the route of infection, proximity of infection as well as virulence factors varies between bacterial strains resulting in different outcomes. Effective treatment of both the viral and the bacterial coinfection is of critical importance. Antiviral treatments deployed initially do not treat bacterial coinfections (McCullers, 2011). The preferred treatment for bacterial coinfections is generally broad-spectrum antibiotics, but this can result in undesirable side effects that will have a negative impact on the normal microflora of the host (Manohar et al., 2020).

Various therapeutic approaches are being used since time immemorial for many health ailments apart from the pharmacological treatment (Anyanwu and Okorie 2017). Approximately eighty percent of the World population still depends upon the use of herbal remedies for their health care (Ekor, 2014). Nigeria and many other countries in West Africa are blessed with several varieties of medicinal plants which are of use for various purposes (Dabai and Muhammad, 2008). *Cochlospermum planchonii* Hook .f. due to its antiviral, antibacterial, anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antipyretic, immunomodulatory and cytoprotective properties is widely used by the traditionalist in treatment of infections (Oladele et al., 2020).

COVID-19 clinical manifestations include fever, fatigue, cough, shortness of breath, and other complications with resultant frightening mortality rate reported globally (WHO, 2020). Also worrying is the pulmonary bacterial coinfection in COVID-19 cases, apart from the associated co-morbidities. Presently, there is yet to be an effective treatment or vaccine that can mitigate/inhibit SARS-CoV-2. Available clinical interventions for COVID-19 are only palliative and limited to support (Oladele et al., 2020). Thus, there is an exigent need for effective and non-invasive treatment. This study will provide valuable information on the antibacterial activity of *Cochlospermum planchonii* roots on pulmonary bacterial co-infection in COVID-19 patients, as an encouragement to pharmaceutical researchers/industries to have a look at it and make safe preparations that can be used by patients, and also provide empirical antibiogram information for clinicians in appropriate management of the infection in the study area.

Materials and Methods

Study Area and Population

Two hospitals were selected for the study and these are; Jos University Teaching Hospital (JUTH) and Plateau State Specialist Hospital (PLSH). The Hospitals are strategically located for access to both urban and rural populations from the 17 Local Government Areas of Plateau State and referrals from neighbouring states of Gombe, Bauchi, Taraba, parts of Kaduna and Nasarawa states in Nigeria. Male and female patients, children and adults that presented with symptoms of COVID-19 who are yet to be confirmed, those that came to be screened for COVID-19 many of whom are close associates/relatives of COVID-19 positive patients and others, as well as COVID-19 positive patients attending the treatment and isolation centers in Jos are recruited. The study was conducted as a cross-sectional analytical in which the subjects were chosen from the population of patients who accessed the COVID-19 treatment/isolation centres at JUTH and PLSH, Jos. A structured questionnaire was used to obtain the social and demographic information from the patients that consented.

Ethical Approval

The study was reviewed and ethical clearance was obtained from both JUTH and PLSH, Jos Ethical Committees. Each of the patients that consented was informed appropriately and voluntarily signed the consent form, and filled the questionnaire administered prior to collection of the sample.

Data and Sample Collection

Using the using the Andrew Fishers's Formula, a total number of 1,620 people who consented from the two major COVID-19 treatment/sample collection centres in Jos, which were JUTH and PLSH, Jos were tested. Sputum samples were taken from each consented COVID-19 patient that presented at the collection/treatment centres. Given the strict COVID-19 protocols, the samples were collected by experienced medics attached to the centres in a wide mouth sample container, labelled appropriately, and immediately placed in an ice pack for onward transportation to the microbiology laboratory for analysis. Demographic data was obtained from consented patients using questionnaires in order to assess the risk factors. All procedures conducted in this study involving human materials were approved by the respective Hospitals' Ethical Committees.

Bacterial Isolation

According to the Centre for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC & P) interim guidelines for collecting and handling clinical specimens for COVID-19 Testing (CDC, 2020), and the WHO directives on risk assessment in handling COVID-19 specimens (WHO, 2020a & b), the sputum samples collected were appropriately labelled, packaged in a leak proof biohazard nylon bag and then placed in an ice packed container. The samples were immediately transported to the microbiology laboratory for processing in a validated biological safety cabinet (BSL-3). The samples were inoculated with appropriate safety procedure in a BSL-3 within 2hrs of collection onto Tryptic Soy Broth (TSB) and the primary isolation of bacterial were performed on Blood Agar, Chocolate agar, MacConkey Agar plates and Cetrimide agar (Oxoid, Ltd, UK). The plates were then incubated at 37⁰C for 24hrs. Blood agar and Chocolate agar were used for the differential isolation and identification of *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae*. Cetrimide Agar plates were used to assess pigment production of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. MacConkey Agar was used for the selective isolation and identification of *Klebsiella pneumoniae*. The culture plates were processed using standard bacteriological procedures (Cheesbrough, 2006). In vitro Identification of bacteria isolates was carried out using a combination of colonial morphologies, Gram stain

characteristics and biochemical reactions as well as the API (Analytical Profile Index) 20E Test System technique (Maina et al., 2014). The sputum samples were further inactivated, decontaminated and concentrated. They were then inoculated onto Lowenstein Jensen (LJ) medium for *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* isolation and smears were made on clean glass slides for Ziehl Neelsen staining technique. The ZN positive samples were confirmed by the GenXpert technique. All the procedures and techniques were according to standards as operated at the North Central Tuberculosis Reference Laboratory, Jos University Teaching Hospital, Jos, Plateau State of Nigeria where the analyses were carried out.

Collection, Identification and Extraction of Plant Material.

Cochlospermum planchonii was gotten from Ogbobutu-Ate village in Abocho, Biraidu District of Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi state, Nigeria. The plant specimen was identified and authenticated by a Botanist in the Department of Plant Science and Biotechnology Herbarium of the Faculty of Natural sciences, University of Jos, and voucher number given. According to Zhang, et al. (2018), each of the fresh plant materials were air-dried at room temperature for six weeks and crushed into powder. A mass of 120g of the plant powder was weighed into 500ml conical flasks and was soaked in 80% methanol. This was left to stand overnight (24 hours) and shaken for 3 hours on a mechanical shaker. The content was filtered using a non-absorbent cotton wool on a Buchner funnel/flask using a vacuum pump. The residue was subsequently subjected to repeated rinsing and filtration with fresh 80% methanol to attain a good level of exhaustive maceration. The filtrate was eventually evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure with the aid of a rotary evaporator and a drying cabinet under a controlled temperature of 60⁰C (30⁰C-60⁰C). The percentage yield of the extract was determined and the extract transferred into a sterile sample container and preserved in the refrigerator at 4⁰C.

Preliminary Phytochemical analysis

The 80% methanol root extract of *Cochlospermum planchonii* was subjected to qualitative analysis using the standard method of Harborne as described by Adeeyo et al., (2018).

Antibiotic Susceptibility Screening

The drug susceptibility test was carried out for all the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates respectively on Mueller-Hinton agar plates and the Kirby-Bauer agar disk diffusion method was used to measure the diameter zones of inhibition following the recommendations of Clinical and Laboratory Standards Institute (CLSI) (CLSI, 2020). A 0.5 Mac Farland standard suspension of the test bacteria was evenly inoculated on the Mueller–Hinton agar by gentle swabbing using sterile swab sticks. The commercial sensitivity discs imbibed with various antibiotics were placed on the surface of the agar and after allowing the plate to stand at room temperature for 30 minutes (pre-diffusion time) the plate was then incubated at 37⁰C for 24 hours. Diameter Zones of Inhibition (DZI) were measured to the nearest millimeters. To determine if a bacteria culture was resistant, intermediate, or sensitive to an antibiotic, its diameter zone of inhibition was compared with the zone diameter interpretative chart of the National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (CLSI, 2020). The antimicrobial agents used in this test were chosen from the commonly prescribed antibiotics for pulmonary bacterial infection in the locality. Their antimicrobial susceptibility to 10 antimicrobial agents from 5 antimicrobial categories (aminoglycosides, carbapenems, cephalosporins, fluoroquinolones, penicillins/ β -lactamase inhibitors) was determined by disk diffusion method, according to the recommendation of CLSI. Characterization of the isolates as Multiple Drug Resistance (MDR) was done according to standardized international terminology presented by European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control (ECDP&C), CDC&P as well as the CLSI guidelines (CLSI,

2020). The test antibiotics used for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* were: Ofloxacin (5 µg), Augmentin (3 µg), Ceftazidime (30 µg), Imipenem (10 µg), Cefepime (30 µg), Piperacillin (110 µg), Gentamycin (30 µg), Ciprofloxacin (5 µg), Cefuroxime (30 µg), and Ceftriazone (30 µg) (Oxoid, UK). A MDR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* phenotype is defined as a bacterium which is resistant to three or more anti-Pseudomonal anti-microbial classes; carbapenems, fluoroquinolones, penicillins/cephalosporins and aminoglycosides (Magiorakos et al., 2012; Saderi and Owlia 2015). An MDR *Klebsiella* phenotype is defined as a bacterium which is resistant to two or more Carbapenems, Cephalosporins and *beta-lactam* antibiotics (CLSI, 2020). *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* ATCC 9027 and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 700603 were used respectively as quality controls.

Also, a drug susceptibility test by the Kirby-Bauer agar disk diffusion method was carried out for all the *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolates on Mueller-Hinton plates and chocolate agar plates respectively. The test antibiotics used for susceptibility study on *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* were: Amoxicillin/Clavulanate (30 µg), Cefotaxime (25 µg), Ceftriazone Sulbactam (45 µg), Cefexime (5 µg), Levofloxacin (5 µg), Ciprofloxacin (5 µg), Imipenem/Clastatin (10/10 µg), Cefuroxime (30 µg), Ofloxacin (5 µg), Erythromycin (15 µg), Gentamycin (10 µg), and Azithromycin (15 µg) (Celtech Diagnostic, Belgium), Penicillin (10 µg), Oxacillin (1 µg) (Oxoid, UK). The results were interpreted according to CLSI guidelines (CLSI, 2020). An MDR *Staphylococcus aureus* phenotype which is also widely known as Methicillin Resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) is defined as a bacterium that develop multiple drug resistance to beta-lactam antibiotics which includes some penams (penicillin derivatives such as methicillin and oxacillin) and cepheims such as the cephalosporins (CLSI, 2020;Gurusamy et al., 2013). An MDR *Streptococcus pneumoniae* is referred to as one that develops resistance to β-lactams, Macrolides and Fluoroquinolones antibiotics (CLSI, 2020). *Staphylococcus aureus* ATCC 6538 and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* ATCC 49619 were used as quality control.

Determination of antibacterial activities of plant extract.

Cochlospermum planchonii root was prepared by dissolving 2g of the extract in 5 ml of 10% (v/v) aqueous Dimethyl Sulfoxide (DMSO) to give an assay stock concentration of 400 mg/ml. Gentamycin (from Sigma, USA) served as positive control and was used at a concentration of 0.2 µg/ml. A stock solution of this control was prepared by dissolving 100mg in 50ml of 10% (v/v) DMSO to give a stock concentration of 2000µg/ml. MDR Clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* obtained from sputum specimens served as the test organisms for susceptibility to the plant extract following standard protocols. A 0.5 Mc Farland turbidity standard (1.5×10^8 CFU/mL) of each bacterium was prepared and used in the course of the study.

The disc diffusion, agar well diffusion and broth micro-dilution methods with microtiter plates were used as described (Jorgensen et al.,2009), to assess the antimicrobial susceptibility of the plant extract by measuring the diameter of zone of inhibition and determining the minimal inhibitory/bactericidal concentrations (MICs and MBCs) according to CLSI standards.

Phytochemical analysis and Antioxidant Studies

The methanol root extract of *Cochlospermum planchonii* was subjected to qualitative phytochemical analysis using the standard method of Harborne as described by Adeeyo *et al.* (2018).

The scavenging activity of the extract against DPPH radical was determined according to the method of McCune and Johns (2002). Total phenolic content (TPC) of the extract was determined using Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (Kumazawa et al., 2004; Belguidoum et al., 2015), while Total Oxyradical (OH⁻) scavenging activity of the extract was measured as described by Smirnoff and Cumbes (Smirnoff and Cumbes, 1989).

Data Analysis

The analyses were carried out in triplicate and the data were expressed as mean \pm standard deviation (STD). The prevalence was determined by descriptive statistics using frequency. The differences between the groups were determined by two-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Values less than 0.05 were set as the level of significance. The statistical analysis was performed by the GraphPad Prism software version 5.00 for windows.

Results

A total number of 1,620 people were tested out of which 148(9.14%), were positive for COVID-19. Among those positive to COVID-19, 82(55.41%) were males, while 66(44.59%) were females. The total number of positive bacterial cultures recorded was 93(62.84%), among which were 52(63.41%) males while the female gender was 41(63.41%) (Table 1).

The distribution of COVID-19 according to age groups showed that eight (8) patients, that is 5.41% were between the ages of 8 to 15 years, while ten (10) patients each, that is 6.76% were within the age range of 16-25 years and 26-35 years respectively. Forty-five (45) patients, that is 30.41% fall within the range of 36-45 years, thirty-nine (39) that is 26.35% fall within 46-55 years, while sixteen (16) that is 10.81% are within the age range of 56-65 years. Patients who are above sixty-five years are 13.51% of the population. Also, people in the age range 56-65 and >65 showed a frequency of 81.25% and 90% respectively of bacterial coinfection, while children between the age range 8-15 years showed 0(0%) pulmonary bacteria coinfection (Table 2).

Distribution of COVID-19 according to co-morbidities showed that sixty-nine (69) COVID-19 patients representing 46.62% have different co-morbidities among which High blood pressure has the highest with 47.82% followed by Diabetes (34.78%) while HIV/AIDS was the least with 4.35% (Table 3, & Table 4).

A total number of ninety-three (93) bacterial pathogens of interest were isolated from the COVID-19 positive patients. This comprised of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* 13 (13.98%), *Staphylococcus aureus* 36 (38.71%), *Streptococcus pneumoniae* 21 (22.58%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* 15 (16.13%), *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* 1 (1.06%), and *Non-Tuberculous Mycobacteria* 7 (7.53%) (Figure 1).

The antibiotic susceptibility of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* showed a percentage sensitivity of 39% for Ofloxacin, Augmentin 0%, Ceftazidime 69%, Imipenem 54%, Cefepime 15%, Piperacillin 92%, Gentamycin 85%, Ciprofloxacin 62%, Cefuroxime 0%, and Ceftriazone 8%. The antibiotic susceptibility of *Klebsiella pneumoniae* showed a percentage sensitivity of 73% for Ofloxacin, Augmentin 53%, Ceftazidime 53%, Imipenem 47%, Cefepime 60%, Piperacillin 47%, Gentamycin 80%, Ciprofloxacin 75%, Cefuroxime 67%, and Ceftriazone 53%. The statistical analysis showed that $p < 0.05$ at a $p = 0.13$, thus, there is a significant difference in the percentage of antimicrobial susceptibility of these commercial discs between *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from COVID-19 positive patients at the 95% confidence level (Figure 2).

Staphylococcus aureus clinical isolates tested on 14 different commercial antimicrobial discs showed that Ofloxacin was the highest with 85% susceptibility followed by Levofloxacin

(82%), while Iminipenem and Cefexine were the least with 12% and 9% susceptibility respectively. A similarly close pattern was observed for *Streptococcus pneumoniae* in which case it exhibited the highest susceptibility of 86% with Ofloxacin, followed closely with 76% with Augmentin. However, Iminipenem showed the least susceptibility at 24%. The statistical analysis showed that $p < 0.05$ at a $p = 0.07$, thus, there is a significant difference in the percentage of antimicrobial susceptibility of these commercial discs between *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolated from COVID-19 Positive patients at the 95% confidence level (Figure 3).

Table 10 showed the susceptibility of methanol extracts of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root to MDR clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. Across the concentration of the extracts, it was observed that at the lowest concentration of 100mg/ml, the organisms exhibited resistance to the extracts with the absolute values of the diameter zones of inhibition (DZI) at 6 ± 0.13 mm. At the concentration of 200mg/ml, the DZI was intermediate at 10 ± 0.32 mm while at a concentration of 400mg/ml, it was susceptible at 18 ± 0.30 mm. Diameter zones of inhibition of extracts are reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Statistical analysis across the different concentrations of the extracts showed that $p < 0.05$ at a $p = 0.0001$. Thus, there is a significant difference between the DZI of the methanol extracts to the clinical isolates with regard to concentration of the extracts at the 95% confidence limit (Table 5).

The results presented in Table 6 showed further antibiogram susceptibility studies on the methanol extracts of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root conducted using the Agar Well Technique. It showed a DZI of 13 ± 0.22 mm on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and 12 ± 0.18 mm for *Staphylococcus aureus* at 200mg/ml concentration. At a concentration of 400mg/ml, the DZI was 17 ± 0.45 mm for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and 18 ± 0.29 mm for *Staphylococcus aureus*.

The MIC and the MBC of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root, was determined for the MDR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus*. The MIC was 62.5mg/ml while the MBC was 125mg/ml to the extract as shown in (Table 7). The MBC/MIC ratio was 2 which showed considerable broad-spectrum activity of the methanolic extract against selected MDR pathogens proving that the extract is not just inhibitory but bactericidal as well (Table 7).

The qualitative phytochemical profile as summarized in Table 8 showed the qualitative phytochemical analysis of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root. The phytochemical profile of the test plant revealed an abundance of tannins, flavonoids, terpenes and other chemical constituents.

The samples' present dose-dependent DPPH scavenging activities was shown in Table 9. The IC_{50} (half maximal inhibitory concentration) of the extract for *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root and vitamin C were 1.71, and 0.17 mg/mL respectively. The DPPH scavenging activities of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root are significantly lower than that of vitamin C, which was used as a reference (Table 9). The total phenolic content of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root was 29.58 ± 6.03 as shown in Table 10. The sample was similarly present dose-dependent total oxyradical scavenging activities. The IC_{50} (half maximal inhibitory concentration) of the extract for *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root and vitamin C were 0.99, and 0.17 mg/mL respectively. The result indicated that the oxyradical scavenging property of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root is significantly lower than that of vitamin C, which was used as a reference (Table 11).

Table 1: Frequency of COVID-19 and Bacterial Isolates in the Study Population.

Gender	No. (%) Tested for COVID	No. (%) Positive for COVID	No. (%) Negative Bacterial Cultures	No. (%) Positive for Bacterial Cultures	No. (%) Negative for Bacterial Cultures
Male	803	82(55.41)	721(48.98)	52(63.41)	30(36.59)
Female	817	66(44.59)	751(51.02)	41(62.12)	25((37.88)
Total	1620	148 (9.14)	1472 (90.86)	93(62.84)	55(37.16)

Table 2: Distribution of COVID-19 With Respect to Age and Number of Bacterial Coinfection

Age Ranges (years)	No. (%) Positive For COVID-19	No. (%) of Positive Bacterial Cultures
8-15	8(5.41)	0(0%)
16-25	10(6.76)	1(10.00%)
26-35	10(6.76)	4(40.00%)
36-45	45(30.41)	31(68.89%)
46-55	39(26.35)	26(66.67%)
56-65	16(10.81)	13(81.25%)
>65	20(13.51)	18(90.00%)
Total	148	93

Table 3: Distribution of the Co-morbidity Status of COVID-19 Patients

Co-Morbidity Status	Frequency(%)
Patients with co-morbidities	69(46.62)
Volunteers with no co-morbidities	79(53.38)
Total	148

Table 4: Distribution of COVID-19 in Patients with Co-morbidities

Co-morbidity	Frequency (%)
Lung Disease/Asthma	5(7.25)
High Blood Pressure	33(47.82)
Diabetes	24(34.78)
HIV/AIDS	3(4.35)
Kidney disease	4(5.80)
Total	69

Figure 1: Distribution of Bacteria Isolates Obtained from Sputum Samples of COVID-19 Positive Patients

Figure 2: Comparison of Antimicrobial Susceptibility of Commercial Susceptibility Discs to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* Isolated from COVID-19 Positive Patients. n = 3.

Since $p < 0.05$ at a $p = 0.13$, there is a significant difference in the percentage of antimicrobial susceptibility of commercial discs to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from COVID-19 Positive patients with regards to the various antibiotics used at the 95% confidence level.

Figure 3: Comparison of Antimicrobial Susceptibility of Commercial Susceptibility Discs to *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolated from COVID-19 Patients. n = 3.

The statistical analysis showed that $p < 0.05$ at a $p = 0.07$, there is a significant difference in the percentage of antimicrobial susceptibility of these commercial discs between *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Streptococcus pneumoniae* isolated from COVID-19 Positive patients at the 95% confidence level (Figure 3.)

Table 5: Mean Diameter of Zone of Inhibition (mm) of Multidrug Resistant *P. aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* to Methanolic Extract of *Cochlospermum planchonii* root using Disc Diffusion.

<i>Cochlospermum planchonii</i> root		
Conct (mg/ml)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
100	6±0.13c	6±0.13c
200	10±0.32b	11±0.30b
400	15±0.38a	15±0.27a
Ctrl	18±0.30d	20±0.48d

The analysis showed that $p < 0.05$ at a $p = 0.0001$. Values with different superscript are significantly different at $p < 0.05$. *± = Standard Deviation; Number of replicates = 3; Ctrl = Gentamycin Control (20ug/ml); Conct = Concentration of Plant Extracts in mg/ml.

Table 6: Mean Diameter of Zone of Inhibition (mm) of Multidrug Resistant *P. aeruginosa* and *S. aureus* to Methanolic Extract of *Cochlospermum planchonii* Root Using Agar Well Diffusion Technique

<i>Cochlospermum planchonii</i> root		
Conct (mg/ml)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>
200	13±0.22b	12±0.18b
400	17±0.45a	18±0.29a
Ctrl	18±0.10a	20±0.41c

The analysis showed that $p < 0.05$ at a $p = 0.0001$. Values with different superscript are significantly different at $p < 0.05$. *± = Standard Deviation; Number of replicates = 3; Ctrl = Gentamycin Control (20ug/ml); Conct = Concentration of Plant Extracts in mg/ml.

Table 7: Mean MIC, MBC and MBC/MIC Ratio of Multidrug Resistant *P. aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* to Methanolic Extract of *Cochlospermum planchonii* root

<i>Cochlospermum planchonii</i> root Conct <i>P. aeruginosa</i> <i>S. aureus</i> Extract (mg/ml)	<i>P. aeruginosa</i>		<i>S. aureus</i>		Gentamycin Ctrl (2µg/ml)	
	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC	MIC	MBC
2000	-	-	-	-	-	-
1000	-	-	-	-	-	-
500	-	-	-	-	-	-
250	-	-	-	-	-	-
125	-	-	-	-	-	-
62.5	-	+	-	-	+	-
31.25	+	+	+	+	+	-
15.6	+	+	+	+	+	+
7.8	+	+	+	+	+	+
MBC/MIC ratio	2	2			2	

*Standard deviation = ±0.00; Number of replicates = 3; Ctrl = Control; - = No Bacterial growth; + = Positive Bacterial growth.

Table 8: Qualitative Phytochemical Profile of *Cochlospermum planchonii* root.

Sap	Tan	Flav	Carb	Ster	Ter	Anth	Car glyc	Amt Obt	% Yield
+	+++	+++	+++	+	+++	-	+++	20.9g	17.4

*Sap = Saponins; Tan = Tannins; Flav = Flavonoids; Carb = Carbohydrates; Ster = Steroids; Ter = Terpenes; Anth = Anthraquinones; Car glyc = Cardiac glycosides; Amt Obt = Amount Obtained; +++ = abundant; ++ = average; + = in traces; - = absent.

Table 9: DPPH Scavenging Activities

Conc. (mg/mL)	Vitamin C	<i>Cochlospermum planchonii</i> root
0.63	96.49±0.74	40.98±5.24
1.25	96.62±0.21	49.75±0.00
2.50	97.04±0.25	67.98±2.87
5.00	97.36±0.49	84.30±1.57
10.00	97.36±0.42	89.73±1.77
IC ₅₀	0.17	1.71

Values are mean ± Standard Deviation of triplicate determination; IC₅₀ = half maximal inhibitory concentration

Table 10: Total phenolic content (TPC)

Sample	TPC GAE/mg
CPR	29.58±6.03 ^a

Values are mean ± Standard Deviation of triplicate determination; GAE = Gallic Acid Equivalent

The total phenolic content of *Cochlospermum planchonii* root was 29.58±6.03.

Table 11: Total hydroxyl Radical Scavenging Capacity

Concentration (mg/mL)	Vit C	<i>Cochlospermum planchonii</i> root
0.31	87.50±2.22	29.17±1.64
0.63	93.56±0.43	32.39±8.58
1.25	94.98±0.33	74.81±3.77
2.50	94.41±0.16	78.13±1.97
5.00	95.64±0.16	79.17±1.66
IC ₅₀	0.17	0.99

Values are mean ± Standard Deviation of triplicate determination

IC₅₀ = half maximal inhibitory concentration.

Discussion & Conclusion

This study has revealed that there are some potentially dangerous bacterial pathogens coinfecting COVID-19 patients which portend grave consequences if overlooked in the

course of disease management by healthcare practitioners. These bacterial coinfections apart from other comorbidities are clearly partly responsible for morbidities experienced during the pandemic due to their pathogenicity (Morens et al., 2008). Despite the clear evidence of the importance of bacterial co-infections in the morbidity of viral respiratory diseases, much less attention was usually paid to it during outbreaks of infections of the respiratory tracts. Zhou et al. (2020) revealed that in the 2019 coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic, 50% of COVID-19 patients that died had bacterial coinfections while Chen et al. (2020) recorded in their study both fungal and bacterial co-infections. Michael et al. (2020) also reported that in severe COVID-19 cases, chronic pulmonary disease (COPD) is one of the risk factors as many COPD patients have underlying chronic bacterial coinfections with the SARS-CoV-2 infection. Reports revealed that 71% of COVID-19 patients on admission received antibiotic drugs in the course of treatment, however, no information is available on the antibiogram of the organisms identified, on the diagnosis of the causative microorganism, or the duration of antimicrobial treatment (Zhou et al., 2020).

The antibiogram pattern observed from this study with the commercial test discs will be a good reference guide by healthcare practitioners with case management in the locality. Antimicrobial treatment of patients with viral pneumonia like the COVID-19 as recommended by the WHO (WHO 2020c), poses huge financial challenge in developing countries like Nigeria with poor economy. Medicinal plants like *Cochlospermum planchonii* roots which abound in Nigeria could be a better alternative. In this study, the antibacterial effectiveness of *Cochlospermum planchonii* roots was demonstrated with impressive diameter zone of inhibition on MDR *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* using the Kirby Bauer disc diffusion, Agar well diffusion and the MIC/MBC assay.

In the present study, the reference antioxidant (Vitamin C) used showed significantly higher free radical scavenging activity than *Cochlospermum planchonii* roots extract at concentrations tested. However, interestingly, the mean antioxidant activity values of the extract revealed that the extract exhibited free radical scavenging activity in a concentration-dependent manner. This is in agreement with the findings of Udegbunam et al. (2015).

Phytochemical analysis of *Cochlospermum planchonii* revealed the abundance of alkaloids, terpenoids, flavonoids, saponins, tannins and reducing sugars useful as potent antimicrobial agents exhibiting bacteriostatic and bactericidal effects against pathogens (Mahizan et al., 2019), as well as health promoting effects (Tanko et al., 2007). The phytochemical constituents observed in this study have great therapeutic potentials as a result of their ability to serve the purpose with minimal side effects often associated with synthetic chemicals (Iwu et al., 1999).

In conclusion, the empirical antibiogram patterns established for the pulmonary pathogens discovered from this study, and the impressive susceptibility and antioxidant activity of *Cochlospermum planchonii* roots proved the effectiveness of this plant. Accordingly, the positive values of this plant regarding the application in traditional medicine have been confirmed. The findings from this study are anticipated to be equally beneficial to everyone dealing with medicinal plant benefits across the world.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST The authors (Ebenezer Kolawole Adeosun*, Emily Akubia Nzeribe, Patience Ogbenyeonu Nwadiaro, Festus Chukwuemeka Onwuliri and Emmanuel Isa Bigwan) declare no conflict of interest/competing interests.

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